

The Analysis of Çeşme Battle (1770) in Terms of Management Functions.

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Abstract

Having management and leadership characteristics, a commander executes management functions. It can be stated that a commander can successfully accomplish the orders given in peacetime by using management functions such as planning, assignment, coordination and control. However, the management functions mentioned above will be insufficient for accomplishing the same orders in wartime. To overcome the change in the battle environment, a commander should also master the leadership functions of leading, gathering for the same purpose and motivation and should use these functions by integrating management functions. Strategic and tactical causes of the Battle of Çeşme, a war between Ottoman and Russia in 1770, are researched in terms of management functions in this article.

Key Words: Organization, Management, Leadership, Strategic Leadership.

1. Introduction

Management is about getting results by taking the work in accordance with the regulations determined (John Kotter, 1999). In short, managerial is about 'Dealing with complexity'. This deal decisions regarding their managers, are always in this particular context. On the other hand, managers make the jobs done by the given authority. So, the 'decision' and 'sanctions' is their right. Today, technological and social developments even cannot lessen the difficulty of company-level coordination of different units. This complexity, depending on the size and structure of the union, is increasing.

Leadership, however, will determine whether the goals and the vision make innovation and change and create trust on people by asking them to do. In short, leadership is about 'Dealing with change'(John Kotter, 1999). Leaders, in doing so, perform their basic concept 'power'. Power, influence others and capable of delivering the desired direction refers to the behavior. There is power in the concept of authority.

Today, technological advances have increased the exchange. Now, duty even vary over the time while managers determine how to perform a duty. This situation led to need for leadership because the prepared initial plan will be inadequate. To do this, commanders, against the current status of each case and without hesitation, and must take the necessary measures as soon as possible.

Commander has to take into consideration in determining the strategic objectives;

- Enemy forces (Opportunity-threatening) condition,
- Harbor types of vehicles and weapons, numbers and activity,
- The geographical situation of frontlines (Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, 1914).

Thus, an exercise in peacetime, with good planning and co-ordination is possible to get good results. Because the environment is not variable.

Events within a pre-planned scenario develops. However, the changes in actual combat environment will require leadership. Leaders, rather than staying with the plan, should determine the appropriate strategies to the changing situation' state.

Commander performs management functions by the means of possessing management and leadership features; a commander succeeds orders which are given during peacetime with the help of planning, staffing, coordination and management functions. Commander has to manage leadership functions, give direction, create common purpose and motivate in order to cope with changes in the environment and has to integrate them.

2. The functions of Management

a. Planning and Direct:

The main way to deal with the mess is detailed planning (John Kotter, 1999) (Abraham Zaleznik, 1999) In line with the strategic objectives, various periods (daily, weekly, monthly or annual) targets are defined. Then, step by step how to perform these objectives are described in detail and the necessary resources are allocated for each step. However, the planning is not only a way of dealing with changes (John Kotter, 1999). After completed, planning will begin to shape. Planning explain definitions for achieving a particular outcome. If the result to be achieved will be change, then the plan will be outdated.

For this, the commander of the change in the environment, primarily intense environment; firstly should show intention and the final result to be achieved, and then direct how to perform this intention in order to determine the strategy. In summary, commander's intent and its strategy that intends to perform, is a leadership function; on the other hand planning activities without losing their way in this direction to ensure progress is a management function. D.W.EISENHOWER quoted " Plans are nothing; but

planning is everything. " He expressed that plan, designed for static conditions, and may lose its validity according to changing conditions. He emphasized that having the ability of defining new objectives and strategy is critical (Tamer Koçel, 2010).

b. Assignment and Creating Common Purpose:

Meeting the requirements of the assignment of tasks and based on this giving orders are the basic management functions that a commander must fulfill. Corresponding to these activities, the leadership function is gathering people under a common purpose (John Kotter, 1999). Leader utilize this function by explaining the goal to his subordinates and allowing them to adopt this goal is realized (M. Watson, 1983). The leadership function will be come out when it comes to the stage to be greeted by the event. If you notice, "design", "model building" activities are being orders while collecting under the common goal requires intense communication (R. Conger, 1991). Commander makes subordinates understand the aim thanks to intensive communication.

Commander's reliability must be an example for people in their command and control (Nuri Conker, 1913). When necessary commander is to command the troops to death. Atatürk's strong personality and heroism in the battle field during the national struggle has led to a better understanding of the messages given by him.

In short giving them clear instructions and giving orders will not guarantee successful results. Changing circumstances may void given the assignment instructions. In such cases, if unit commander was able to collect subordinates under a common purpose, then the subordinates avoid falling to despair.

c. Coordination / Control and Motivation

Director realizes the execution of the plan by using mechanisms of coordination and control. For this reason, compares plan with the results obtained. This will be completed with the inspection and meeting tools. Later deviations from the plan are found to identify solutions to problems. Leader makes coordination to prevent recurrence of the problem (Abraham Zaleznik, 1999).

Leaders inspire and motivate subordinates to create the common goal (John Kotter, 1999). Despite the changes and obstacles in the specified direction, provides the same vigor progress by appealing to people's sense of values (Warren Bennis 1991).

One must be Reliable, dedicated, an example, and have communication skills to lead Our subordinates to death. Although a portion of leadership is developed later, personal characteristics is known to play a role greatly. In particular, charisma, known to be an innate characteristic, is extremely important for the Turkish culture. despite being very successful as a leader Some people also may find it difficult to fulfill management functions. coordination and control operations can be tedious and even seem overwhelming for who can read the Change very good, can create alternative solutions to different situations, and can interact with subordinates in high quality.

3.Çeşme Raid

On 7 July 1770, the Russian Navy burned the Mediterranean fleet which consists of one galley, five war galleon and 25 warships in the Çeşme harbor without allowing them to move. What was the reason for this? In fact, a series of mistakes would be more accurate to speak. This causes regarded as strategic and tactical military context would be more accurate.

Strategically;

I. The Ottoman Navy was one of strongest navy numerically during the era. Navy Captain is changed continuously, and this was seen as a position of authority as a gift. The same problem occurred even before the Çeşme raid and Hüseyin Pasha, who was appointed Navy Captain, had a career of ship building engineering. Thus, the fate of the Ottoman Navy was given to a commander (leader) who was recognized by subordinates as untrusted and lacking of experience in regards of sea war tactics.

II. Navy ships are not well equipped and the crew was reduced by half. This crew did not know anything about and experience of maritime and naval warfare. Although Navy Captain was aware of this situation, he did not take the necessary measures. Although the results of internal analysis were known, appropriate measures could not be taken by leaders.

III. During this period, the Cezayirli Gazi Hasan Pasha as well as other sailors were under the command of Huseyin Pasha. despite Cezayirli Gazi Hasan Bey's opposition of the military operation, Navy Captain confined the ships to the port and led to all fleet to extinct. Navy Captain did not rely on higher-level dependent and he was not be flexible in order to understand the degree of external threat. The threat analysis was not done. In addition, he was close to the projections.

IV. Hüsamettin Pasha did not show the required reaction against the Russian Navy. The most important reason is that he certainly did not trust the Navy and thought that ships were not ready for war. In fact, Hüsamettin Pasha analyzed their own parties, but he could not show the courage and initiative to take measures. This commander thought their fleet of

vessels could not fight in the open sea and therefore has kept the ship in port.

Yet he could save navy from extinction by taking advantage of the enemy's weakness and the sea state. Here, it seems, a leader behaved according to the internal analysis and he was unable to identify the weaknesses and environmental conditions. Perhaps most importantly, he expressed distrust, thus his commanders and soldiers admitted defeat.

Tactically;

I. Despite all the warnings, Navy Captain made the ships pulled to to the harbor on top of each other, and then the ship could not maneuver and did not have the opportunity to fire.

II. He took the measures to protect the safety of the ships by guarding port of Çesme, however; all because of a different tactical approach of the enemy, fleet was destroyed.

4. Results In this event;

- Geographical situation of the enemy's weakness has not been utilized by analyzing Internal and external threats,

- Although the staff was untrained and inexperienced and initiative was not shown to take the necessary measures. In addition, if morale, motivation and initiative have been given to the staff, navy could be saved from extinction.

5. Analysis:

The analysis of Çeşme Battle in terms of management functions with respect to strategic and tactical reasons;

Planning / Guidance

Planning should begin after the completion of the process to direct. Because plan defines the work to be done. If you change the result to be achieved in the plan, this plan will be outdated. In this event;

I. Detailed planning was not executed.

II. Effective and competent leadership not displayed (Knowledge-Skill-Effectiveness inadequate),

III. Threats and Environmental Conditions have not analyzed, the A-B-C Plan does not exist, be shortsighted and lack of timely decisions,

IV. Shortsighted move

b. Creating Common Purpose

In short giving them clear instructions and giving orders will not guarantee successful results. Changing circumstances may void given the assignment instructions. In such cases, if unit commander was able to collect subordinates under a common purpose, then the subordinates avoid falling to despair.

I. Communication and lack of

coordination (consultation),

II. Team work is not available,

III. Distrust of Staff,

IV. Lack of deploying credential,

V. Uneducated Staff.

c. Motivation

I. Initiative not given to Staff

II. Values not given importance

III. Not being encouraged,

IV. Success disbelief.

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